

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF DYES

Dye no.	R_f	λ_{max} nm	% Exhaustion		$\nu_{C=O}$ cm^{-1}	ν_{CH_2} cm^{-1}	$\nu_{N=N}$ cm^{-1}	$\nu_{SO_2N_2}$ cm^{-1}	ν_{NH} , ν_{HO} cm^{-1}
			Nylon	Polyester					
D-1	0.73	490	73	72	1 660	1 480	1 430	2 180	2 980–3 500
D-2	0.79	500	71	70	1 645	1 475	1 435	2 125	2 980–3 400
D-3	0.77	490	75	74	1 650	1 485	1 430	2 120	3 300–3 440
D-4	0.74	500	73	76	1 655	1 470	1 425	2 130	2 280–3 400
D-5	0.79	425	68	69	1 645	1 475	1 425	2 115	2 430–3 450
D-6	0.76	420	65	67	1 645	1 485	1 435	2 125	3 260–3 420
D-7	0.68	435	71	69	1 640	1 480	1 430	2 115	3 260–3 420
D-8	0.70	435	70	68	1 650	1 475	1 425	2 130	3 300–3 440

was rolled properly and dropped in to the beaker. The beaker was then placed vertically and the rotatory carrier inside the tank was allowed to rotate in the glycerin bath whose temperature was raised at rate of 2° per min up to a final temperature at 130°. The dyeing was continued for 60 min at 130° under pressure. After cooling over a period of 1 h, the beaker was removed from the bath and washed with water. The pattern was washed several times with cold water. The above dyed pattern was further treated with a solution of detergent (0.2 g) and sodium carbonate (0.1 g) in water (100 ml) at 80° for 30 minutes, and after washing thoroughly water, it was dried.

2% shade on nylon : The materials used were as follows : Nylon fabric, 2 g ; amount of dye solution under study at pH 3, 40 ml (0.1%, w/v) ; MLR, 1 : 30 ; total volume of dye bath, 60 ml. The dye bath⁷ with MLR 1 : 30 was adjusted to pH 3 using acetic acid. The sample of nylon fabric was introduced in the dye bath at room temperature and its temperature slowly raised to 100° in 15 minutes. The fabric was worked up in dye bath at 100° for 1 h and then washed with warm water, cold water and dried.

Reactive disperse dyes containing sulphonyl azido group were separated on tlc using n-butanol–pyridine–water (25 : 25 : 15) solvent system. The results are given in Table 2.

The electronic spectra (DMF) were determined using a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer using concentration of dye solution 2×10^{-3} M (Table 2).

The percentage exhaustion of the dyes were performed using the standard procedure. The results are given in Table 2.

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Analytical Reagent TQA—Photometric Determination of Copper(II) in Alkaline Medium and Trace Analysis in Steel†

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THE paper describes the synthesis and use of *N*-(phenyl)-2-thioquinaldinamide as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of trace amount of copper(II) in synthetic materials.

Experimental

Copper(II) solution was prepared by dissolving pure electrolytic grade Cu-wire in aqua regia and sulphuric acid and standardised iodometrically.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing 100 μ g ml⁻¹ of copper(II), 2 M KOH (1.5 ml) was added to adjust the pH to 11.0. Then a 0.1% alcoholic reagent solution (5 ml) was added and the volume made up to 25 ml. The absorbance of the violet complex was measured at 525 nm after 2–3 min against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The copper(II) complex showed absorption maximum at 520–530 nm at pH 11.0. The complex showed constant absorbance for 1.5–6.0 ml of 0.1% reagent. A 5 ml of 0.1% solution was always used. The absorbance was constant upto 4.0 ml of 2 M KOH and measured at pH 11.0. The complex

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obeyed Beer's law in the range 0.4–15 ppm of Cu^{II} , the optimum range⁸ being 2–11 ppm at 525 nm. The molar absorptivity was $4.6 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The photometric error was 2.7% following Ayres' equation.

Copper (6 ppm) was determined in the presence of many diverse ions. More than 100-fold excess of Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , UO_2^{II} , VO_2^{II} , Ti^{IV} , Al^{III} , In^{III} , Fe^{III} , Bi^{III} , As^{III} , Mn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Sn^{II} and Hg^{II} did not interfere. No interference was observed due to Fe^{III} , Bi^{III} , As^{III} , Mn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} in the presence of 5 ml of 10% TEA. 25 ppm of Ag^{I} did not interfere. Except EDTA and cyanide with 30 ppm as tolerance limit, most of the anions did not interfere when present in more than 200-fold excess.

Determination of copper in alloy steel: Steel sample (0.5 g) was dissolved in 3M sulphuric acid (50 ml) and digested on a hot-plate with repeated additions of the acid. The solution was treated with a few drops of concentrated nitric acid for complete digestion. The clear solution so obtained was evaporated to a thick mass and then cooled, diluted with 50 ml water, filtered and washed with dilute acid. The filtrate and washings were cooled and transferred quantitatively into a 100 ml volumetric flask and volume made up to the mark. To an aliquot (5–10 ml) were added 0.1% reagent (5 ml) and 10% TEAHCl solution (5 ml) and pH was adjusted to 11.0. The volume of the solution was made up to the mark with requisite amount of ethanol and absorbance measured at 525 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of copper was found to be 0.32, 0.10 and 0.08% with a deviation of $\pm 0.01\%$ (certified: 0.32, 0.10 and 0.08% Cu in BAS steel).

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Micro-determination of Rhenium with α -Mercaptobenzothiazole

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THERE are many chelating extractants¹ with sulphur atoms which can coordinate with metal ions. Sulphur containing organic compounds are still in use for extractive studies because of the coloured

complexes they form with the metal ions. Several sulphur-substituents of the oxygen of commonly employed chelating extractants have also been tried and their complexes are very often more strongly coloured and thus suitable for colorimetry. Recent literature survey reveals that such reagents have not received attention for the analysis of rhenium. The present paper reports an extractive method of determination of rhenium based on the formation of intensely coloured complex between the metal ion in its lower valent state and α -mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT).

Experimental

A standard stock solution of rhenium containing 1 mg Re/ml was prepared by dissolving potassium perrhenate (Specpure, Johnson Mathey) in water containing a few drops of dilute sulphuric acid, and lower concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared by appropriate dilutions.

Solutions of other ions were prepared by dissolving their commonly available sodium or potassium salts (B.D.H.) in distilled water. A 2% fresh solution of α -mercaptobenzothiazole (purified with alcohol) was prepared in acetone.

A 20% solution of stannous chloride (B.D.H.) was made in 1 : 1 HCl and diluted to 100 ml with distilled water.

Preparation of samples: Synthetic samples are prepared by mixing perrhenate and other metal ion solutions to get the desired composition.

Reverberatory flue dust samples from copper manufacture, containing no rhenium, were mixed with a solution of known rhenium content and dried in an oven. After fusion of the dust with sodium peroxide (8 times the weight of sample) the leach was neutralised with concentrated sulphuric acid and made slightly alkaline. It was boiled and the hydroxide precipitate was washed with distilled water. The filtrate was adjusted to 7 M HCl and rhenium determined as described below.

Procedure: To a solution containing $\leq 100 \mu\text{g}$ Re were added 10 M HCl (14 ml), 2% α -mercaptobenzothiazole (1 ml) and 20% $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution (1 ml) and the final volume was made up to 20 ml with distilled water. The solution was mixed gently, then allowed to stand for 10 min and the coloured species was extracted with 10, 10, 5 ml of chloroform equilibrating each time for 2 min. The combined solvent extract was filtered and made up to 25 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the orange coloured species was measured at 380 nm in 1 cm silica cells using a DU-2 spectrophotometer against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

In presence of stannous chloride, heptavalent rhenium is reduced to lower valence (IV, V) in acid solution which forms an orange coloured complex